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Mini Review

Physicochemical And Organoleptic Properties of Ekavimshatika Guggulu

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ABSTRACT

Ekavimshatika Guggulu is an Ayurvedic formulation mentioned in Bhavprakasha for treatment of various disorders like Kushta, Grahani, Gridhrasi, Bhagna etc. In the present study physicochemical properties and organoleptic properties of Ekavimshatika Guggulu was studied. All these studies are carried out based on standard procedure

INTRODUCTION

Aushadha is considered one of the four fold constituents of *Chikitsa Chatushpada*⁽¹⁾ and can help to break disease *Samprapthi* in *Ayurveda*. The main aim of treatment is to maintain the equilibrium of *Dosha, Dhatu, Mala* and *Agni*. *Aushadi Nirmana* is important concept explained in ancient texts. It is divided into two branches 1) *Ras Shastra* and 2) *Bhaishajya Kalpana*. *Bhaishajya Kalpana* consists of primary formulations like *Panchavidha Kashaya Kalpana* and other secondary formulations like *Churna, Vati, Guggulu* etc among all these *Kalpanas* now a days *Guggulu Kalpana* is widely

used. One amongst the *Guggulu Kalpana* is *Ekavimshatika Guggulu*. *Ekavimshatika Guggulu* is mentioned in *Bhavprakasha Madhyam Khand* in *Kushta Adhyay*.⁽²⁾ The name itself suggests that the formulation contains 21 herbs including *Guggulu*. *Ekavimshatika Guggulu* is used in treatment of *Kushta, Kurmi, Grahani, Gridhrasi, Bhagna* etc. Here all the herbs are pounded into fine powder separately and taken in equivalent quantity. Then *Shuddh Guggulu* is added in amount equivalent to the sum of powder of all the herbs and powdered. Then all drugs are mixed and ghee is added after which tablets are made. Here we will discuss the

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physicochemical and organoleptic properties of *Ekavimshatika Guggulu*.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

PROCUREMENTS OF RAW MATERIAL

For preparation of *Ekavimshatika Guggulu* raw material was collected from local market. Each raw drug was packed separately and labelled with name, part and date of collection. Each drug was shaded dried.

AUTHENTICATION OF EKAVIMSHATIKA GUGGULU

The procured samples of individual raw drug were authenticated by Sheetal Analytical

Laboratory, Pune, Maharashtra. The authentication certificate number issued for drug by laboratory is A.M-378/01 B-25.

PREPARATION OF EKAVIMSHATIKA GUGGULU

Ekavimshatika Guggulu was prepared as per *Bhavprakash*. The dried drugs were powdered separately in pulverizer and filtered through mesh no 120 and then each one of them is measured and taken in equal quantity. *Shuddha Guggulu* is added an amount equivalent to sum of powder of all the drugs and pounded in to homogenous compound. *Ghee* is added to homogenous compound and then rolled into form of tablets. The ingredients used are mentioned below.

Table No 1. Ingredients of *Ekavimshatika Guggulu*.

Sr No.	Local Name	Latin Name	Family Name	Part / Used
1.	<i>Shunthi</i>	Zinziber Officinale	Zingiberaceae	Rhizome
2.	<i>Pippali</i>	Piper longum Linn.	Piperaceae	Fruit
3.	<i>Vidanga</i>	Erbeliaribes	Myrsinaceae	Fruits
4.	<i>Devdaru</i>	Cedrus Deodaru	Pinaceae	Bark
5.	<i>Saindhav lavan.</i>	Rock Salt	Nacl	Whole
6.	<i>Chitrakmool</i>	Plumbago Zeylanica	Plumbaginaceae	Root/ Bark
7.	<i>Ajwain</i>	Trachyspermum ammi (L.)	Apiaceae	Seed
8.	<i>Maricha</i>	Piper Nigrum	Piperaceae	Fruit
9.	<i>Abhaya(Haritaki)</i>	Terminalia chebula Retz	Combretaceae	Fruit
10.	<i>Guggulu</i>	Commiphora Mukul	Burseraceae	Gum resin
11.	<i>Aamalaki</i>	Emblica Officinalis	Euphorbiaceae	Fruit
12.	<i>Bibhitaki</i>	Terminalia Bellirica	Combretaceae	Fruit
13.	<i>Jeeraka</i>	Cuminum Cyminum	Apiaceae	Seeds
14.	<i>Vacha</i>	Acorus calamus	Acoraceae	Mool
15.	<i>Ativisha</i>	Aconitum Heterophyllum	Ranundaceae	Root tubers
16.	<i>Kushtha</i>	Saussurea Lapa	Asteracea	Root
17.	<i>Chavya</i>	Piper Officinarum	Piperaceae	Fruit
18.	<i>Ela</i>	Elletaria cardamomum.Linn	Zingiberaceae	Seeds
19.	<i>Yavakshara</i>	Hordeum Vulgare	Poaceae	Whole
20.	<i>Musta</i>	Cyprus rotundus	Cyperaceae	Rhizome
21.	<i>Ajmoda</i>	Apium leptophyllum	Apiaceae	Seed

ORGANOLEPTIC PROPERTIES OF EKAVIMSHATIKA GUGGULU

Colour, odour, taste and shape of *Ekavimshatika Guggulu* are mentioned below

Table No 2.Organoleptic properties

Colour	Brownish Colour
Odour	Pungent
Taste	Bitter and Astringent
Shape	Rounded vati

PHYSICOCHEMICAL ANALYSIS OF EKAVIMSHATIKA GUGGULU

1.Loss on drying at 110°C-

an accurately weighed 1g of *Ekavimshatika Guggulu* formulation was taken in tarred glass bottle. The Percentage moisture content of sample was calculated with reference to shade dried material

2.Total ash content-

weighed accurately 2g of *Ekavimshatika Guggulu* formulation was added in crucible at a temperature of 600°C in muffle furnace till carbon free ash was obtained.It was calculated with the reference to the air dried drugs.

3.Water soluble extract-

5gm of *Ekavimshatika Guggulu* was macerated with 100ml of distilled water in closed flask for 24 hours shaking frequently.The solution was filtered and 25ml of filtrate was evaporated in a tarred flat bottom shallow dish,further dried at 100°C and weighted.The percentage of water soluble extract was calculated with the reference to air dried drugs.

4.Alcohol soluble extract-

1gm *Ekavimshatika Guggulu* was macerated with 20ml alcohol in closed flask for 24 hours.With frequent shaking, it was filtered rapidly taking precaution against loss of alcohol 10ml of filtrate was then evaporated in a tarred flat bottom shallow dish, dried at 100°C and weighted. The percentage

of alcohol soluble extractive was calculated with reference to air dried drugs.

Table No 3:Physicochemical properties of Ekavimshatika Guggulu.

pH	4.79
Loss on Drying at 110°C	12.45%
Total Ash Content	5.50%
Water Soluble Extract	30.54%
Alcohol Soluble Extract	9.77%

CRITICAL QUALITY ATTRIBUTES OF EKAVIMSHATIKA GUGGULU

Table no 4.CQA's of Ekavimshatika Guggulu

Hardness	1.95 kg/cm
Disintegration time	20 min 27 sec
Friability test	0.001 %

DISCUSSION

The drug *Ekavimshatika Guggulu* was prepared as per *Bhavprakash*.And it was studied for physicochemical and organoleptic properties.The observed values of the physicochemical properties are Loss on drying(12.45%),Total ash content(5.50%),Water soluble extract(30.45%),Alcohol soluble extract(9.77%).Organoleptic properties of *Ekavimshatika Guggulu* reveals that its colour is brownish in tablet form and its taste is bitter and astringent and smell is pungent.Hardness of tablet was satisfactory.

CONCLUSION

In present study the ingredients used in drug were authenticated and the drug was studied for physicochemical and organoleptic properties.The study reveals that the formulation *Ekavimshatika*

Guggulu meets minimum quality standards and can be used in *Gridhrasi, Kushta, Kurmi etc.*

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PICTURES OF MAKING OF EKAVIMSHATIKA GUGGULU

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